

Pr. prof. dr. Viorel Sava
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THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE PATRIARCHATE OF ROMANIA AT THE BEGINNING OF PREPARATION OF THE HOLY AND GREAT COUNCIL OF THE ORTHODOX CHURCH (1902-1932)

Ioannis LADAS

Dr.

Facultatea de Teologie Ortodoxă, Salonic, GRECIA

Abstract:

The Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church is admittedly one of the most important Orthodox ecclesiastical events of the 21st cent. The Council's 2016 convening was finally made possible after a very long and arduous preparatory process of circa 93 years, in which process the Patriarchate of Romania appears to have played an important and constructive role. In fact, the Church of Romania, in 1920, shortly before the official preparation begins, dispatched Prof. Dragomir Demetrescu to the Ecumenical Patriarchate with the mandate to exchange views on the possibility of convoking a "Council of the Orthodox Churches", and to propose potential issues to be considered in such a Council. Since then, the Church of Romania has responded positively to all the relevant invitations of the Great Church of Constantinople and participated constructively in all the preparatory bodies and phases of the Holy and Great Council, while the Romanian Primates - from Patriarch Myron to Patriarch Daniel - demonstrated a profound synodical awareness and fought devotedly for the unity and cooperation of the Orthodox Churches. The current article has a double scope: on the one hand, it presents the historical contribution of the Patriarchate of Romania at the beginning of preparation of the Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church, and on the other hand, it attempts to evaluate it.

Keywords: *Holy and Great Council, Ecumenical Patriarchate, Patriarchate of Romania, Inter-Orthodox Relations*

The Ecumenical Patriarchate began working on the issue of convening a Council of the Orthodox Churches at the beginning of the 20th century, when the Ecumenical Patriarch Joachim III (1834-1912) made specific proposals in front of the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate on important ecclesiastical issues. This was done in order to prepare a Patriarchal and Synodical Encyclical, which would be sent to the individual Orthodox

Churches¹. In the first official text of the Ecumenical Patriarchate on the inter-Orthodox and inter-Christian relations of the 20th century, the Church of Romania responded positively and even made specific proposals. Metropolitan Iosif (1829-1909), Primate of the Church of Romania, and the members of the Holy Synod responded by acknowledging that the exchange of letters between the Orthodox Churches contributed to the maintenance of the dogmatic and canonical unity, which is based on the teachings of the Lord². Nevertheless, the circumstances at that time were not favourable for convening such Council and, in the meantime, the relationships between the Orthodox Churches changed drastically, to the extent that even the meetings of their representatives became (almost) impossible.

After the end of the First World War, the Ecumenical Patriarchate began to work again on the issue of convening the “Ecumenical or Pan-Orthodox Council”. Meanwhile, on December 18, 1919, the bishop Myron Cristea of Casansebes (1868-1939) was elected as Metropolitan - Primate of the Church of Romania and played an important role in both the promotion of the ecclesiastical independence of the Church in the territories of Romania, as well as in the strengthening of relations with the individual Orthodox Churches. The same year, the Romanian Professor of the Orthodox Theological School of Bucharest, Dragomir Demetrescu (1852-1926), visited Greece and, together with the Archbishop of Athens Meletios Metaxakis (1871-1935), later Ecumenical Patriarch, the members of the Holy Synod of the Church of Greece and professors from Theological School of the University of Athens, including the later Archbishop of Athens Chrysostomos Papadopoulos (1868-1938), discussed the necessity of convocation of a Pan-Orthodox Council. They agreed that the Association of the various Orthodox Theologians of the individual Orthodox Churches should meet and work on the issues that concern the Church and prepare the ground for the convening of the Council.

¹ Patriarchal and Synodical Encyclical “to their Beatitudes and Holiness's the Patriarchs of Alexandria and Jerusalem, and to the Most Holy Autocephalous sister-Churches in Christ, in Cyprus, Russia, Greece, Romania, Serbia and Montenegro” protocol No 3636 and dated June 12, 1902, in: *Αί περί τῶν σχέσεων τῶν Αυτόκεφάλων Ὀρθοδόξων Ἐκκλησιῶν καί περί ἄλλων γενικῶν ζητημάτων Πατριαρχική καί Συνοδική ἐγκύκλιος τοῦ 1902: Αἱ εἰς αὐτήν ἀπαντήσεις τῶν Ἁγίων Αυτόκεφάλων Ὀρθοδόξων Ἐκκλησιῶν καί ἡ ἀνταπάντησις τοῦ Οἰκουμενικοῦ Πατριαρχείου*, Patriarchal printing house, Constantinople, 1904.

² Answer of the Church of Romania to the Patriarchal and Synodical Encyclical protocol No 3636 and dated June 12, 1902, in: *Αἱ περί τῶν σχέσεων τῶν Αυτόκεφάλων Ὀρθοδόξων Ἐκκλησιῶν...*, pp. 42-53.

Upon his return to Bucharest, Professor Dragomir Demetrescu informed the Romanian ecclesiastical and political circles for the discussions that took place in Athens and they rejoiced over it, foretelling a bright future for the Orthodox Churches. The following year, 1920, the Church of Romania, under the guidance of Metropolitan Myron and in consultation with the Minister of Religious Affairs, decided synodically to send an appropriate delegate to the Ecumenical Patriarchate and to other local Orthodox Churches, not only for the purpose of holding consultations on the convening of a Council of the Orthodox Churches, but also to define the issues that had to be addressed in it. Thus, Professor Dragomir Demetrescu was recruited again and visited the Ecumenical Patriarchate, where he was received by the Locum Tenens of the Patriarchal See, Metropolitan Dorotheus of Bursa (1861-1921), and the members of the Holy and Sacred Synod, who agreed and blessed the idea. Afterwards, he went to Athens and appeared in front of the Holy Synod of the Church of Greece, in the presence of the Royal Commissioner, who enthusiastically accepted the relevant proposal and, after discussion, they signed a protocol. Then, he visited the Church of Serbia, where he received the same warm welcome, as in this Church there were urgent issues that needed to be resolved, such as the marriage of clergy after ordination and the second marriage of widowed clergy. The professor also visited the Synod of Karlovci and the Sofia, where the ecclesiastical circles were in favor of convening a Council, as they envisioned an end to the schism³. All discussions concluded in unanimous agreement and the argument that the Orthodox Church should become a living and active Church in the community of believers was put forward, providing a favorable solution to all issues of mutual concern to Orthodoxy⁴.

The occasion for the official - long term preparation of the Holy and Great Council was presented by the issue of ecclesiastical Calendar. The Ecumenical Patriarchate Meletios Metaxakis decided to invite all Orthodox Churches to send representatives to Constantinople in order to set up an inter-orthodox Committee⁵, which would prepare (suggestively) the pan-orthodox issues (including the issue of ecclesiastical Calendar), with the aim of convening a "Great Council" for their adjustment and resolution⁶. In fact, the

³ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress in Constantinople (May 10 - June 8, 1923), Patriarchal printing house, Constantinople, 1923, pp. 43-48.

⁴ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., pp. 43-44.

⁵ The inter-orthodox Committee later named Pan-Orthodox Congress.

⁶ Minutes of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate B' 70, pp. 28-29, §3; The Ecumenical Patriarchate for the New Calendar, in: *PANTAINOS – Official Bulletin of the Alexandrian Patriarchate*, 15 (10 March 1923), pp. 179-180; Patriarchal letters to their

Ecumenical Patriarch had realized that the need to convene a Council had become absolutely necessary and as he had pointed out in his enthronement speech was very glad as he ascended to the Patriarchal See and found the relevant request from the Church of Romania⁷.

The Church of Romania participated in the Pan-Orthodox Congress with a two-member delegation, consisting of archimandrite Iuliu Scriban (1878-1949) and Senator Petre Drăghici, who had even prepared a detailed proposal on the issue of church calendar⁸. Moreover, after invitation of the Ecumenical Patriarch, the Pan-Orthodox Congress was attended by the Romanian professor Dragomir Demetrescu, who was at that time in Constantinople.⁹ Demetrescu stated during the meetings of the Congress that the gathering was intended to prepare the ground for the convening of a “Pan-Orthodox Council”. According to him, the idea of convening such a Council wasn’t new, but after the First World War its convening became urgently necessary for the individual Orthodox Churches: 1. for the observance of unity in faith, 2. for the predominance of a uniform administrative system, and 3. for their consolidation in the future¹⁰.

During the Congress the Romanian representative, archimandrite Iuliu, noted that the Churches of the “Orthodox Federation” came together after so many centuries of isolation to discuss and resolve many important issues which remained unresolved for a long time, emphasizing that isolation is a threat for the unity, because in the absence of relationships one begins to feel like a stranger, not perceived by others and finally separated, as is the result for those who have nothing in common. The issue he mentioned is psychological, since those who live far away from each other get used to the distance and feel stranger to each other. This psychological issue, he continued, exists among the Churches, indicating that particular circumstances have already been introduced in every Orthodox Church, which in future may threaten unity and push us to feel strangers to each other. Archimandrite Iuliu concluded that the Congress should start a new period, which would strengthen the spirit of unity and lay the foundations for work

Beatitudes and Holiness's Primates of the Orthodox Churches of Alexandria, Jerusalem, Antioch, Jerusalem, Serbia, Cyprus, Greece and Romania protocol No 872 and dated February 3, 1923, in: *PANTAINOS...*, 15 (17 March 1923), pp. 195-197.

⁷ V. STAVRIDIS, *Οἱ Οἰκουμενικοὶ Πατριάρχαι - 1860 – Σήμερα. Ἱστορία καὶ Κεῖμενα* [The Ecumenical Patriarchs - 1860 - Today. History and Documents], Society for Macedonian Studies publications, Thessaloniki, 1977, pp. 466-467.

⁸ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 2.

⁹ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 41.

¹⁰ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 41.

that would be maintained in the future. Then, archimandrite Iuliu submitted to the Congress a proposal of the metropolitan Nikolae of Transylvania (1882-1955) regarding the solemn celebration of the 1600th anniversary from the convening of the First Ecumenical Council (325-1925), which was unanimously accepted and approved to be included in the Agenda¹¹.

During its 8th session (June 1, 1923), the Pan-Orthodox Congress considered the above proposal and decided: 1. to gladly accept the proposal of the metropolitan Nikolae of Transylvania, for a solemn celebration of the 1600th anniversary of the convening of the First Ecumenical Council in 1925, 2. to ask for the Ecumenical Patriarchate's initiative to celebrate this event with dignity by the Orthodox Church as a whole, not only locally, but also by convening a Pan-Orthodox Council in order to resolve the issues that concern the Orthodox Churches and 3. to express the wish at the celebration to invite all the Churches, which accepted the Nicene Creed¹².

The convening of the Pan-Orthodox Congress was a milestone for the modern history of the Church as well as a starting point for continuous and closer communication of the individual Orthodox Churches¹³. It was until this moment that the theoretically existing unity of the Orthodox Churches manifested in practice¹⁴, as the representatives of the Churches met and took common decisions. The delegation of the Church of Romania stated meeting is of utmost importance. This is a beginning; Congresses such as this must become a permanent statute through which the orthodox concentration will be further strengthened. For this reason, he commended the Ecumenical Patriarch Meletios for the initiative to convene the Congress and thanked him for starting the Congress' work, wishing to follow more fruitful Congresses¹⁵.

On July 18, 1923, the Presider of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate, metropolitan Nikolaos of Caesarea (1862-1927), later metropolitan of Chalcedon, officially informed the Orthodox Churches about the decision of the Pan-Orthodox Congress and stated that the Holy and

¹¹ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 33.

¹² Decision No VI of the Pan-Orthodox Congress in Constantinople (June 5, 1923): Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 221.

¹³ Address by metropolitan Kallinikos of Kyzikos at the closing session of the Pan-Orthodox Congress, in: *Εκκλησιαστική Αλήθεια* 43 (June, 9 1923), p. 193; Address by metropolitan Iakovos of Durrës at the closing session of the Pan-Orthodox Congress: Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 193.

¹⁴ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., p. 191.

¹⁵ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., pp. 194-195.

Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate had already accepted it¹⁶. The Holy Synod of the Church of Romania met in regular session in the autumn and on November 5, 1923 and discussed the proposal to convene an Ecumenical Council. However, the Holy Synod decided that the issue of convening an Ecumenical Council should follow its preparatory way, given the fact that not only there are several serious difficulties, but also a part of the Orthodox Churches was pressured by harsh circumstances, which could damage the universality of the Council¹⁷. Therefore, the Patriarch of Romania suggested the postponement of the Ecumenical Council for a more appropriate time and suggested that the celebrations for the 1600th anniversary of the convening of the First Ecumenical Council (325-1925) be held locally by the Church of Romania¹⁸. To this decision contributed the fact that the Romanian delegation to the Pan-Orthodox Congress witnessed "hateful scenes" against the Ecumenical Patriarch and the fact that there was no Ecumenical Patriarch at that moment¹⁹.

On May 27, 1924, the Ecumenical Patriarch Gregory VII (1850-1924) invited the Orthodox Churches to participate in the first "General Pan-Orthodox or/and Ecumenical Council" after so many centuries in Jerusalem on Pentecost 1925. The Church of Romania gladly accepted the decision of the Ecumenical Patriarchate²⁰ and, on January 16, 1925 the Patriarch of Romania Myron informed the Ecumenical Patriarchate that the Holy Synod decided to accept Jerusalem as the place of convocation of the Council, but does not wish to discuss at the Council issues relating to fundamental

¹⁶ Letter of metropolitan Vasilios of Caesarea, Presider of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate, to the Metropolitan Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, protocol No 3692 and dated July 18, 1923: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

¹⁷ Answer of the Metropolitan Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, protocol No 446 and dated December 11/24, 1923 to the letter of metropolitan Vasilios of Caesarea, Presider of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate, protocol No 3692 and dated July 18, 1923: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

¹⁸ "Ἑτεραι Ἐκκλησίαι [Other Churches]", in: *PANTAINOS...*, 16 (2 Φεβρουαρίου 1924), p. 76.

¹⁹ Minutes and decisions of the Pan-Orthodox Congress..., pp. 194-195.

²⁰ Letter of Metropolitan Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, protocol No 348 and dated September 24, 1924: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

teachings of the faith (number of sacraments, denaturation, the doctrines formulated by the seven Ecumenical Councils)²¹.

Nevertheless, the Synod could not be convened on Pentecost 1925, but on July 30 of that year the patriarchal value and honor was attributed to the Church of Romania. The relevant Patriarchal Letters arrived in Romania at the end of September, accompanied by an official mission of the Ecumenical Patriarchate, which consisted of the metropolitans Ioakeim of Chalcedon (1876-1927), Germanos of Sardis and Pisidia (1885-1945) and the first Draguman of the Patriarchate Spyridon Constantinidis²². At the enthronement of Patriarch Myron and with the opportunity of representatives of the Orthodox Churches gathering in Bucharest discussions took place on the issue of convening a Council. All participants, without exception, agreed with the existing need of convening a Council and asked the representatives of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to propose to the Ecumenical Patriarch to take the relevant initiative, which would be in order with the protocols of the Orthodox Church. Later, the Patriarch Myron, during his visit to Constantinople, emphasized the need to prepare the Council, both in private conversations and in his official address to the Ecumenical Patriarch²³.

The following year, the Ecumenical Patriarchate returned to the decision of convening a Great Council, not only because further postponement would be inefficient, but also because over the centuries many issues have arisen “increasingly” and “rather urgently”²⁴. The Patriarch of Romania, immediately after receiving the Patriarchal Letters, convened an extraordinary meeting of the Holy Synod on March 6, 1926 and expressed its contentment, as it found that the idea of convening an Ecumenical Council had matured and it was only waiting for the right moment for its realization. The Patriarch Myron in his answer mentioned the importance and necessity of convening an Ecumenical Council and stated that he warmly wished for its faster convening, as he considered it to be “definitively imposed for the

²¹ Letter of Metropolitan Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, protocol No 1150 and dated January 16, 1925: Minutes of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate B' 72, pp. 201-202, §6.

²² See: “Church of Romania”, in: *Ὁρθοδοξία* 31 (May 1926), pp. 45-46.

²³ Report of Pre-Council's Committee protocol No 1464 and dated August 31, 1929: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive 1952/142.5.3, pp. 2-3.

²⁴ Patriarchal letters to the Primates of Orthodox Churches protocol No 2957 and dated December 10, 1925, in: *Ὁρθοδοξία* 1 (May 31, 1926), pp. 24-26.

Orthodoxy”²⁵. Nevertheless, he informed the Ecumenical Patriarchate that the Holy Synod, after discussion, was in favor of postponing the convening of the Ecumenical Council, as the appointed day did not meet the necessary conditions. The Church of Romania maintained that the issues which would be examined should have been adequately studied, so that the Council could resolve them definitively. They expressed concern that, in the alternative, the hopes which the Church had from the convening of the Council would be dashed. Thus, the Holy Synod proposed and requested that the future assembly of the Orthodox Churches not be called an Ecumenical Council, but to have the character of a Preliminary and Preparatory Conference of an Ecumenical Council, in which the ecclesiastical calendar issue would be definitively resolved. This Conference, among others, would provide the opportunity to approach and get to know the Orthodox Hierarchs, who had been alienated from the borders and the various political conditions. In the same spirit, Bishop Titus of Targoviste (1886-1971), assistant bishop at that time of the Archdiocese of Bucharest and later metropolitan of Bucovina, visited Constantinople as a representative of Patriarch Myron and pointed out how urgent and imperative the convocation of the Pre-Council was and the significance attached to the initiatives of the Ecumenical Patriarchate²⁶ by the Church of Romania. However, according to some information, the Church of Romania intended to participate in an Ecumenical Council in case the Ecumenical Patriarchate decided finally to convene it²⁷.

The Ecumenical Patriarchate accepted the proposal to convene a “Preliminary Conference” and the Ecumenical Patriarch Basilios (1846-1929) on May 1, 1926 announced to the primates of Orthodox Churches that the “Ecumenical Council” had been appointed to be preceded by a “Preliminary Conference of representatives of all the Orthodox Autocephalous Churches”, which would receive the title and status of “Pre-Council”²⁸.

²⁵ Answer of the Patriarch Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, protocol No 988 and dated March 30, 1926, to the Patriarchal letters protocol No 2957 and dated December 10, 1925: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive 1926/38.3, pp. 1-3.

²⁶ Report of Pre-Council's Committee protocol No 1464 and dated August 31, 1929, *ibid*, pp. 2-3.

²⁷ Report from the Greek Ambassador of Bucharest to the Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs protocol No 3032 and dated March 7, 1926: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive 1926/38.3, p. 1.

²⁸ Patriarchal letters to the Primates of Orthodox Churches protocol No 1234 and dated May 1, 1926, in: *Ἐκκλησία* 4 (May 10, 1926), p. 19; Memorandum of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate protocol No 1245 and dated May

The preparatory work for the convening of the Pre-Council waned from 1926 to 1928, but the Ecumenical Patriarchate had not given up on the decision taken. The reason for the restarting of efforts was the fact that, in 1926, the Church of Romania unilaterally decided to celebrate Easter according to the results of astronomical science, ie on April 4 of the New Calendar, unlike the rest of the Orthodox Churches and contrary to the direction given by the Ecumenical Patriarchate that Easter would be celebrated on May 2 of the arranged calendar²⁹. The following years, 1927-1928, the Patriarch of Romania Myron, because of the situation that had arisen, promptly asked the Ecumenical Patriarchate for its opinion, which in turn resumed preparatory proceedings³⁰.

In 1929, the Patriarch of Romania highlighted the long-standing necessity for an immediate convocation of a Pre-Council to the metropolitan Chrysanthos of Trapezous and Exarch of Lazica (1881-1949), who went to Bucharest to discuss the “Albanian ecclesiastical situation”³¹. In fact, he begged Ecumenical Patriarch “as the First to convene the fastest Pre-Council, if so approved by the Church of Constantinople, the head of the Orthodox Churches”. During the same year, the Patriarch of Romania sent to the Ecumenical Patriarchate archimandrite Filaret Ioku, who personally handed a letter to the Ecumenical Patriarch and also orally stated the request for convening a Pre-Council. In his letter he pointed out that it was an absolute necessity that the Ecumenical Patriarch, “as the center of the spiritual unity of Ecumenical Orthodoxy”, convenes immediately a Conference consisting of one or two representatives of each Orthodox Church in Constantinople or elsewhere, which would set the Easter celebration time for at least 4 or 5 years, to avoid annual costs. The Patriarch Myron noted that a joint decision regarding the celebration of Easter would ensure the fraternal relationship between the Churches and pointed out that this situation is confusing, giving rise to differences between the individual Orthodox Churches and resulting to the damage of the unity and the external life of the Church. According to him, the Conference of the Orthodox Churches was to be convened as soon as possible, because in Romania calendars were printed very early (in July

5, 1926: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

²⁹ Report of Pre-Council's Committee protocol No 1710 and dated June 21, 1928: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive 1952/142.5.3.

³⁰ Telegram of the Patriarch of Romania Myron to the Ecumenical Patriarch protocol No 1542 and dated July 6, 1928: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive 1952/142.5.3.

³¹ “Church of Constantinople”, in: *PANTAINOS...*, 21 (21 March 21, 1929), p. 196; “Pre-Council”, in: *PANTAINOS...*, 21 (October 3, 1929), p. 674.

and August). Therefore, the decision of the Conference had to be taken till this time and the celebration of Easter to be announced in time, so that it is accepted by all the Orthodox Churches³². In addition, the Patriarch of Romania sent a letter through the Chief Secretary of the Synod of the Church of Romania letter requesting for the second time to be informed of the Ecumenical Patriarchate's views on the issue of the Pre-Council and the celebration of the coming Easter³³.

In October 1929, the Ecumenical Patriarchate under the guidance of the newly elected Patriarch Photios II (1874-1935), decided before the Pre-Council to convene an Inter-Orthodox Committee, whose task would be to determine the jurisdiction of the future Pre-Council, including the Agenda, the issues of ecclesiastical Calendar and Easter and the exchange of relevant views on them (preliminary)³⁴. Nevertheless, in February 1930, Bishop Titus of Targoviste visited the Ecumenical Patriarchate together with archimandrite Iuliu Scriban and delivered to Patriarch Photios a letter from the Primate of the Church of Romania, in which he asked for the permission of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to allow the representatives of the Orthodox Churches (that would be in Athens on the occasion of their participation in the Conference of the Christian Brotherhood of Youth) to hold a meeting and exchange views on general ecclesiastical issues, which of course would not bind the individual Orthodox Churches³⁵. The Church of Romania made this move as it considered that the convening of the Inter-Orthodox Committee would not take place soon and, for this reason, taking advantage of the opportunity, proposed the joint consideration of the issues³⁶. Ecumenical Patriarch Photios, however, put forward the Inter-Orthodox Committee of Mount Athos, which would satisfy the desire of Patriarch Myron. At the same

³² Letter of Patriarch Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, without No and dated April 2, 1929: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive B'35 (1929).

³³ Report from the Greek Consul General in Constantinople (Sakellaropoulos) to the Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs protocol No 115 and dated July 10, 1929: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive B 1930/ B/35/VI B/35.

³⁴ Memorandum of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate dated October 28, 1929: Y.D.I.A., Central Service Archive B 1930/ B/35/VI B/35.

³⁵ Bishop Titus of Targoviste informed the Ecumenical Patriarch by letter that he would visited Constantinople on the way to Athens for attending to the Conference of the Christian Brotherhood of Youth

³⁶ Letter of Patriarch Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, to the Ecumenical Patriarchate Photios, protocol No 488 and dated February 19, 1930: Minutes of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate B' 76, p. 108, §4.

time, he assured Bishop Titus that the Commission would be convened in the near future and therefore what Patriarch Myron had written would be realized. He also expressed the view that the representatives of the Orthodox Churches that would gather in Athens should not and could not come to a meeting and exchange views on general ecclesiastical issues, as the Patriarchate could not accept the discussion of issues concerning all Orthodoxy with the occasion of one conference. It should be noted that the Romanian bishop Titus of Targoviste wished the Committee to be convened in Constantinople, as he stated “it would be nice if the Inter-Orthodox Committee should convene at the base of the Pan-Orthodox Center, at the Ecumenical Patriarchate”³⁷. In April of the same year, archbishop Nektarie of Chernivtsi and metropolitan of Bukovina (1875-1935) visited the Ecumenical Patriarchate and he stated that the Church of Romania as well as the whole Orthodox Church is looking forward to the time when the Church of Constantinople, as the Primordial Church, will invite the Orthodox Churches to meet together on the great issues, which have occupied the Orthodox Church for long time. Bishop Titus noted characteristically: “Do not forget that you do not only manage the fortunes of the Church of Constantinople, but that you are also the one who directs the whole Orthodox Church”. Patriarch Photios replied that he had “deep knowledge” and that he had taken the decision to convene an Inter-Orthodox Committee on June 8, decision for which he was first informed of the occasion³⁸.

Indeed, the Committee convened at the Sacred Monastery of Vatopedi on Mount Athos and deemed “necessary the immediate commencement of preparations for a Pan-Orthodox Council and drafted a preliminary template for a list of its basic agenda items”,³⁹ which consisted of 17 topics of canonical, dogmatic, liturgical and ecclesiological content, without binding character and with the possibility of modification in the future. In addition, it issued the first joint Announcement of the Orthodox Churches of the 20th century, in which it was emphasized that the work was carried out “in the spirit of brotherly love and unanimity”, a fact which could be considered “as

³⁷ Minutes of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate B' 76, p. 108, §4.

³⁸ Minutes of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate B' 76, p. 206, §2.

³⁹ “History of the Holy and Great Council”, <https://www.orthodoxcouncil.org/preparation-of-a-council-a-history>.

an auspicious beginning of closer cooperation between the local Orthodox Churches”⁴⁰.

The convening of the Preparatory Inter-Orthodox Committee produced a profound impression on the Orthodox Clergy and People of Romania. Patriarch Myron noted that this beginning will mark a decisive starting point for the history of the Church⁴¹. The Romanian Church participated in this Committee with a two-member delegation, consisting of Bishops Lucian of Roman (1872-1953) and Titus of Targoviste.⁴² Bishop Lucian stated during the meetings that

„our discussions yesterday and today show that we have not been together for a long time and show the great need to gather more often. Having not met for centuries, we must not dwell on regulatory issues, and in the absence of explicit articles of Procedure we are obliged to follow the way of Logic”⁴³.

On January 7, 1931, Patriarch Photios announced to the Orthodox Churches that the “General Orthodox Pre-Council” will be convened on the Sunday of Pentecost June 19, 1932, as the intermediate period of one and a half years was considered sufficient for the study of the issues⁴⁴. However, the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate met on June 2, 1932, 17 days before the date of the convocation of Pre-Council, and examined for the umpteenth time all the objective facts and the real circumstances under which the whole of the Orthodox Churches was living. Patriarch Photios was forced for reasons beyond his willing to propose the postponement of the Pre-Council⁴⁵ at a more appropriate time, guided by the fullest success of it works. Contributing factor to this decision, of course, apart from the “difficult circumstances”, was the possibility of certain disagreements arising during the Pre-Council, which would be completely useless for the Orthodox Church.

⁴⁰ Minutes of preparatory Inter-Orthodox Committee of the Holy Orthodox Churches (June 8 - 23, 1930), Patriarchal printing house, Constantinople, 1930, pp. 151-152.

⁴¹ Answer of the Patriarch Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, protocol No 316 and dated May 27, 1930: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

⁴² Telegram of the Patriarch of Romania Myron, Primate of the Church of Romania, to the Ecumenical Patriarch Photios dated May 12, 1930: Archive of the Chief Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod of Ecumenical Patriarchate.

⁴³ Minutes of preparatory Inter-Orthodox Committee ..., p. 66.

⁴⁴ Patriarchal letters to the Primates of Orthodox Churches protocol No 266 and dated January 7, 1931, in: *Ὁρθοδοξία* 6 (February 1931), pp. 102-103.

⁴⁵ V. ΣΤΑΥΡΙΔΙΣ, *Οἱ Οἰκουμενικοὶ Πατριάρχαι - 1860 – Σήμερα. Ἱστορία καὶ Κείμενα* [The Ecumenical Patriarchs - 1860 - Today. History and Documents], Kyriakidis publications, Athens, 2005, pp. 567-588.

In conclusion, the convening of the Holy and Great Council, almost a century after the first related efforts, is admittedly one of the most important Orthodox ecclesiastical events of the 21st century, since first time after a millennium, representatives of the individual Orthodox Autocephalous Churches met, discussed and made decisions together, after decades of accumulation of internal problems, which related to the visible unity of Orthodoxy. In this spirit, Patriarch Daniel of Romania pointed out during his address at the Opening Session of the Holy and Great Council that

„The Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Churches is simultaneously a rare event and the beginning of normality, because synodality is a canonical rule of the life of the local Churches, in order to express the unity of Orthodox faith, of sacramental life and of canonical discipline of the One, Holy, Universal (Catholic) and Apostolic Church”⁴⁶.

Admittedly, to the great success of the convocation and the impressive completion of the indeed extremely difficult task of the Holy and Great Council, the Church of Romania played an important role, given the fact that it responded positively to all the relevant invitations of the Ecumenical Patriarchate and participated constructively in all the preparatory bodies and phases of the Holy and Great Council, since the Romanian Primates (from Patriarch Myron, who had been characterized as an old and fearless worker of the idea of a new Ecumenical Council⁴⁷, to the current Patriarch Daniel, who took part in the Holy and Great Council) demonstrated a profound synodical awareness and fought devotedly for the unity and cooperation of the Orthodox Churches.

⁴⁶ Address of His Beatitude Daniel, Patriarch of Romania, at the Opening Session of the Holy and Great Council, Crete, Monday, 20 June 2016, <https://holycouncil.org/opening-patriarch-daniel>.

⁴⁷ Minutes of preparatory Inter-Orthodox Committee..., p. 46.